

Table SM6. Canonical correspondence analysis (CCA) for macrobenthic taxa abundance data based on 59 stations of the continental slope and São Paulo Plateau at Santos Basin, SW Atlantic. Environmental variables are listed according to the forward selection method. Significance levels are based on a Monte Carlo test (999 permutations).

CCA	Axis 1	Axis 2	Axis 3		
Eigenvalue	0.2429	0.0990	0.0634		
Taxa-environment correlation	0.4322	0.1761	0.1128		
Cumulative % variance	0.4322	0.6084	0.7212		
F	16.9509	7.0407	4.4473		
p	0.001	0.015	0.026		
Environment variable	Inter-set correlation with			F	p
	Axis 1	Axis 2	Axis 3		
Seawater temperature (°C)	-0.977474	0.02592	-0.05429	12.2420	0.001
Mean particle size (mm)	-0.466236	-0.72466	0.25576	3.5254	0.003
Biopolymeric carbon (mg g ⁻¹)	0.539459	0.54326	0.14768	2.8804	0.003
Carbonate content (%)	0.161750	-0.42945	0.18825	2.0454	0.023
Protein:Carbohydrate	-0.510360	-0.34442	-0.60885	2.1645	0.029
Phaeopigments:Chlorophyll-a	-0.425162	-0.08934	0.64999	1.8529	0.044
Grain sorting	0.396581	-0.01674	-0.33982	2.4599	0.004
Dinosterol (µg.g ⁻¹)	-0.002538	0.46194	0.03893	2.0654	0.032
Latitude (°S)	0.226442	-0.07722	0.40809	7.4301	0.001
Clay content (%)	0.578750	0.40622	-0.14335	1.5887	0.100